

STUDIES IN γ -KETONIC ACIDS. PART I.

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Bürker (*Ann. chim. phys.*, 1882, **26**, v, 435) first effected the condensation between benzene and succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and obtained β -benzoylpropionic acid. This opened up a new route for synthesising β -aroylpropionic acids and substituted β -aroylpropionic acids by using the appropriate components.

Clemmensen reduction of the β -aroylpropionic acids (I, R=H) gives rise to γ -arylbutyric acids (II, R=H) which can be cyclised to the corresponding 1-ketotetrahydronaphthalene (III). Further Clemmensen reduction of the keto compound leads to the formation of a tetrahydronaphthalene which can be dehydrogenated with selenium to the corresponding naphthalene derivative.* Alternatively, a new alkyl group can be introduced by the action of the Grignard reagent on the ester of β -aroylpropionic acid, (I, R=alkyl) followed by dehydration, dehydrogenation and ring closing when 1-alkyl-4-ketotetrahydronaphthalene derivative is obtained. A

repetition of the same series of reactions would lead to 1 : 4-dialkyltetrahydronaphthalene derivative.

We have studied the condensation of phenol and various phenolic ethers with succinic anhydride with the object of synthesising various naphthalene derivatives and also with a view to fill up *lacunae* in the works of other authors. An attempt has also been made to prepare acenaphthene derivatives by condensing 7-methoxy-1-ketotetrahydronaphthalene with bromoacetic ester in the presence of zinc, and subsequent ring-closing, but

* On the other hand, by the action of the Grignard reagent on the keto-compound followed by dehydrogenation and selenium treatment an α -alkyl naphthalene (IV) may be obtained.

the condensation by Reformatsky's reaction resulted in such a poor yield that further progress was rendered impossible.

Rosenmund and Schapiro (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, **272**, 313) have found that anisole condenses with succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene medium to give γ -*p*-methoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid. We have found that the reaction proceeds smoothly in acetylene tetrachloride medium at the ordinary temperature (*i.e.* 25°) with almost theoretical yield. The keto-acid gives a semicarbazone (m.p. 185-86°).

By the reduction of this keto-acid by Clemmensen's original method (*Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 1837) Haworth and Sheldrick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1951) obtained γ -*p*-methoxyphenylbutyric acid (m.p. 63-64°). They converted the acid into the chloride and effected the ring-closing with the help of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The ring-closure proceeds smoothly with almost theoretical yield with phosphorus pentoxide in benzene medium and gives 7-methoxy-1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (m.p. 62°, semicarbazone, m.p. 221°). Further reduction of the ring ketone by Clemmensen's method gives 1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene-7-methyl ether (b. p. 103°-105°/5.5 mm.) identical with the compound obtained by Schroeter and others (*Annalen*, 1922, **426**, 83) by methylating tetrahydro- β -naphthol with dimethyl sulphate and alkali.

1-Keto-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene gives on condensation with methyl magnesium iodide the completely dehydrated product, 1-methyl-7-methoxy-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (b. p. 124°/5.5 mm.), which on dehydrogenation with selenium (Diels, Gadke and Kording *Annalen*, 1927, **459**, 1), gives 1-methyl-7-methoxynaphthalene (m. p. 46°). Haworth and Sheldrick (*loc. cit.*) did not isolate the intermediate product. They submitted the product obtained by treatment with the Grignard reagent direct to selenium dehydrogenation and obtained 1-methyl-7-methoxynaphthalene (m. p. 47°-48°; picrate, m.p. 117°). Again 1-methyl-7-methoxy-3:4-dihydronaphthalene on catalytic hydrogenation readily gives 1-methyl-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene (b. p. 116°/8 mm.).

Pyrogallol trimethyl ether condenses with succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in acetylene tetrachloride to give γ -2-hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid (m. p. 152°), one methyl group being knocked off during the reaction. The keto-acid on reduction by Clemmensen's method gives γ -2-hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid (m. p. 103°), dehydration of which with 85% sulphuric acid gives 1-keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-hydroxy-6:7-dimethoxynaphthalene (m. p. 155°; semicarbazone, m.p. 226°). Further reduction of this ring-ketone by

Clemmensen's method gives 1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-hydroxy-6:7-dimethoxynaphthalene.

Perkin and Ormerod (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1902, 81, 234) condensed resorcinol dimethyl ether with the ester of half chloride of succinic acid in a mixture of nitrobenzene and carbon disulphide in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride and obtained in very poor yield 2:4-dimethoxybenzoylpropionic acid after hydrolysing the resulting crude ester. Perkin and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 506; *cf.* Dalal and Nargund, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1937, 14, 408) obtained the same acid with apparently better yield by effecting condensation in carbon disulphide medium or without any solvent. But they did not mention the formation of any other product in this reaction. We have found that resorcinol dimethyl ether condenses readily with succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in acetylene tetrachloride medium at 50-60° and the product after crystallisation from water does not melt at a definite temperature and it gives ferric chloride colouration. The distilled product is dissolved in ether, and washed with ice-cold dilute caustic soda solution. On acidification with hydrochloric acid in the cold γ -2-hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid is obtained identical with the acid prepared by Perkin and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) under more drastic conditions. The ester obtained after distilling off the ether is the ester of γ -2:4-dimethoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid (m.p. 66°), the hydrolysis of which gives γ -2:4-dimethoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid (m.p. 147°; semicarbazone, m.p. 166°). Reduction of this acid by Clemmensen's method gives γ -2:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid (m.p. 48°). Attempts have been made to cyclise this acid with dehydrating agents like phosphorus pentoxide, concentrated sulphuric acid, fuming stannic chloride, fused zinc chloride and by treating the chloride of this acid with anhydrous aluminium chloride but without success.

Phenol condenses with succinic anhydride in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride in acetylene tetrachloride medium at 130°-140° and gives rise to γ -2-hydroxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric acid (m.p. 145°), identical with the acid previously obtained by Rosenmund and Schapiro (*loc. cit.*) from 2-oxy- β -chloropropionylbenzol of Meyer and Zutphen (*Ber.*, 1924, 57, 200) over the nitrile. Reduction of this keto-acid by Clemmensen's method gives rise to γ -o-hydroxyphenylbutyric acid (m.p. 67°) with almost theoretical yield, identical with the compound obtained by Schroeter (D.R.P., 562,827, Dec. 21, 1928) from 5-keto-tetrahydronaphthalene. This acid could not be cyclised by dehydration with concentrated sulphuric acid, phosphorus pentoxide, fuming stannic chloride or by the acid chloride method.

We have observed that γ -2:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid and γ -*o*-hydroxyphenyl-butyrlic acid could not be cyclised by various dehydrating agents. This is most probably due to the presence of *ortho* or *para* directing group *meta* to the position marked * in which cyclisation must take place as will be evident from the formulæ.

These are not the only instances where similar orienting influence has inhibited cyclisation. Numerous other examples might be cited from the works of other authors. Thus Walsh and Weizmann (*J. Chem. Soc.*; 1910, 97, 685), Graves and Adams (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2439), Gardner and Adams (*ibid.*, 1923, 45, 2455), and Jacobson and Adams (*ibid.*, 1924, 46, 1312) observed a similar difficulty in the formation of anthraquinones from those benzoylbenzoic acids which contain an *ortho* or *para* directing group *meta* to the position in which condensation must take place. This difficulty was particularly pronounced in the case of phenol derivatives probably on account of the ease with which sulphonation took place. Attempts made by Feiser and Bradsher (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1738) to cyclise the butyric acid derivatives of diphenyl namely, γ -(4-methoxy-3-phenyl)-butyric acid, with sulphuric acid through the acid chloride were unsuccessful and they ascribed their failure to the above causes.

EXPERIMENTAL.

γ -*p*-Methoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric Acid.—Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (120 g.) was slowly added to a mixture of anisole (47.5 g.), succinic anhydride (40 g.) and acetylene tetrachloride (160 c.c.) kept cool in ice-water. The temperature was not allowed to rise above 40°. The mixture was left overnight and then decomposed by the addition of ice and dilute (1:1) hydrochloric acid. The excess of anisole and acetylene tetrachloride were removed by distillation in steam. The residue in the flask solidified on cooling. It was filtered, digested with sodium carbonate solution and the filtrate was acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid in the cold, when the keto-acid was precipitated. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 146°, yield 67 g. (Haworth and Sheldrick gives m.p. 147-48°).

(Found : C, 63.33; H, 5.72. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_4$: C, 63.46; H, 5.76 per cent). The keto-acid gave a semicarbazone which was crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 185-86°. (Found: N, 16.07. $C_{12}H_{15}O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.88 per cent).

γ -p-Methoxyphenylbutyric Acid.—The keto-acid (40 g.) was reduced with zinc amalgam prepared, from zinc filings (120 g.), and hydrochloric acid by heating for 8 hours. The product which solidified when kept overnight was dissolved in sodium carbonate and the solution precipitated with hydrochloric acid. The acid crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in beautiful crystals, m. p. 61°, yield theoretical. (Haworth and Sheldrick gives m. p. 63-64°). (Found : C, 68.41; H, 7.02. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$: C, 68.04; H, 7.21 per cent).

1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-7-methoxynaphthalene.—The above acid (20 g.) dissolved in anhydrous benzene (100 c.c.), was heated on the boiling water-bath with phosphorus pentoxide (60 g.). After removing benzene, the residue was treated with powdered ice and distilled in steam, when the ketone was obtained as an oil in the distillate. It was extracted with ether and on removing ether it solidified when kept in a vacuum desiccator. It crystallised from petroleum ether (b. p. 60-80°) in square plates, m.p. 62°, yield 15 g. (Haworth and Sheldrick gives m. p. 66-67°). (Found: C, 75.32; H, 6.58. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_2$: C, 75.00; H, 6.81 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 221°. (Found: N, 18.32. $C_{12}H_{15}O_2N_3$ requires N, 18.02 per cent).

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydro-7-methoxynaphthalene.—The above ketone (8 g.) was heated with amalgamated zinc (35 g.) and hydrochloric acid for 24 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water, dried and distilled at 103.5°/5.5 mm.; yield 5 g. (Found: C, 81.66; H, 8.61. $C_{11}H_{14}O$ requires C, 81.48; H, 8.64 per cent).

Condensation of Methyl Magnesium Iodide with 1-Keto-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—The ketone (27 g.), dissolved in anhydrous ether (100 c.c.), was added to the Grignard reagent prepared from 5 g. of magnesium and 22 c.c. of methyl iodide in equal volume of anhydrous ether. The mixture was left overnight and the magnesium compound decomposed with ice cold 10 % dilute sulphuric acid and then extracted with ether. The ethereal extract, washed with sodium bisulphite and water was distilled at 124°/5.5 mm., yield 21.5 g. The distilled product turned pale brown within 15 minutes and was found by analysis to be completely dehydrated. It decolourised potassium permanganate solution almost instantaneously. (Found: C, 82.47; H, 8.24. $C_{12}H_{14}O$ requires C, 82.75; H, 8.04 per cent).

1-Methyl-7-methoxynaphthalene.—The above product was dehydrogenated with selenium in the usual manner by heating for 30 hours at 310–330°. The product was extracted with ether, washed with 5% caustic soda solution, then with water and finally the ethereal solution was dried and distilled at 134°/7mm. as a colourless liquid which solidified when kept in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 46°, yield 4.5 g. (Haworth and Sheldrick gives m.p. 47–48°). (Found: C, 83.69; H, 7.09. Calc. for C₁₂H₁₂O: C, 83.72; H, 6.97 per cent). The *picrate* crystallised from absolute alcohol as orange needles, m.p. 117°. (Found: N, 10.42. C₁₈H₁₅O₈N₃ requires N, 10.47 per cent).

Catalytic Hydrogenation and Formation of 1-Methyl-7-methoxy-1:2:3:4-tetrahydronaphthalene.—Freshly distilled 1-methyl-7-methoxy-3:4-dihydronaphthalene (9.5 g.) in alcohol (30 c.c.) was hydrogenated in presence of 0.2 g. platinum oxide. The calculated quantity of hydrogen was practically absorbed within an hour. The product was then transferred into the conical flask and the portion adhering to the flask was extracted with ether and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Ether and alcohol were removed and the reduced product was distilled at 116°/8 u.m., yield 8 g. (Found: C, 81.54; H, 9.07. C₁₂H₁₆O requires C, 81.81; H, 9.09 per cent).

γ-2-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxyphenyl-γ-ketobutyric acid was obtained from pyrogallol trimethyl ether (52 g.), succinic anhydride (30 g.) and acetylene tetrachloride (120 c.c.) using anhydrous aluminium chloride (90 g.), yield 51 g. It crystallised from water as colourless needles, m.p. 152°. It gives violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 56.55; H, 5.34. C₁₂H₁₄O₆ requires C, 56.69; H, 5.51 per cent).

γ-2-Hydroxy-3:4-dimethoxyphenylbutyric acid was prepared from the above keto-acid (30 g.) by heating with amalgamated zinc (90 g.) and hydrochloric acid for 8 hours. The product was extracted with ether, the extract washed with water, dried and the ether removed. The residue solidified in a vacuum desiccator, yield almost quantitative. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°), m.p. 103°. (Found: C, 60.41; H, 6.76. C₁₂H₁₆O₅ requires C, 60.00; H, 6.66 per cent).

1-Keto-1:2:3:4-tetrahydro-5-hydroxy-6:7-dimethoxynaphthalene.—The above acid (6 g.) and sulphuric acid (85%, 25 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for about 1 hour. The mixture was then poured into ice and the product was extracted with ether. The extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and with water. The ethereal solution was dried and the ether removed. The ring ketone crystallised from ether in colourless fine needles, m.p. 155°, yield 4 g. (Found: C, 65.04; H, 6.37. C₁₃H₁₄O₄

requires C, 64.86; H, 6.30 per cent). The *semicarbazone* crystallised from alcohol in brown crystals, m.p. 226°. (Found: N, 15.51. $C_{13}H_{17}O_4N_3$ requires N, 15.05 per cent).

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydro-5-hydroxy-6:7-dimethoxynaphthalene.—The preceding ring ketone (6 g.) was heated for 24 hours with amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product was extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution dried, ether removed and the residue distilled at 148-154°/5.5 mm., yield 3 g. (Found: C, 69.51; H, 7.80. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 69.23; H, 7.69 per cent).

Condensation of Succinic Anhydride with Resorcinol Dimethyl Ether.—Powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (120 g.) was gradually added to a mixture of succinic anhydride (40 g.), resorcinol dimethyl ether (60 g.) and acetylene tetrachloride (160 c.c.) with constant shaking. The mixture was then heated at 50-60° for 3 hours, kept overnight and then treated with powdered ice and dilute hydrochloric acid (1:1). Excess of resorcinol dimethyl ether and acetylene tetrachloride were removed by steam distillation. The solid residue was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and the mixture of keto-acids precipitated by acidification with hydrochloric acid, yield 85 g.

γ -2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric Acid.—The crude mixture (40 g.) of keto-acids was refluxed for about 8 hours on the sand-bath with absolute alcohol (100 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.). Excess of alcohol was removed by distillation and the residue extracted with ether, the extract washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and then with 10% dilute ice-cold caustic soda solution. The caustic soda solution on acidification with cold concentrated hydrochloric acid gave not the ester but the keto-acid. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 154°. yield 5 g. It gives violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found: C, 59.12; H, 5.52. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 58.92; H, 5.35 per cent). The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 198°. (Found: N, 14.69. $C_{12}H_{15}O_5O_3$ requires N, 14.94 per cent).

Ethyl γ -2:4-Dimethoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyrate.—The above ethereal solution was dried, ether removed and the residue was distilled at 198-200°/5 mm., m.p. 66°, yield 32 g.. (Found: C, 63.49; H, 6.93. $C_{14}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 63.15; H, 6.76 per cent).

γ -2:4-Dimethoxyphenyl- γ -ketobutyric Acid.—The above ester (28 g.) was refluxed for 3 hours with caustic potash (10%, 150 c.c.). The alkaline solution on acidification gave the keto-acid. It was crystallised from water, m.p. 147°, yield 23 g. (Found: C, 60.33; H, 6.05. $C_{12}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 60.50; H, 5.88 per cent). The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from

glacial acetic acid, m.p. 166°. (Found : N, 13.92. $C_{13}H_{17}O_5N$, requires N, 14.23 per cent).

γ-2:4-Dimethoxyphenylbutyric Acid.—The keto-acid (30 g.) was heated for 9 hours with amalgamated zinc (90 g.) and hydrochloric acid. The product was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water and dried, ether removed and the residue distilled at 199-201°/5 mm. It solidified when kept in a vacuum desiccator, yield 18 g. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-70°), m.p. 49°. (Found : C, 63.92 ; H, 7.16. $C_{12}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 64.29 ; H, 7.14 per cent).

γ-o-Hydroxyphenyl-*γ*-ketobutyric acid was prepared from succinic anhydride (20 g.), phenol (21 g.), acetylene tetrachloride (100 c.c.) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (60 g.) as usual. The mixture was finally heated at 130-140° for 2 hours. Excess of phenol and acetylene tetrachloride was removed by steam distillation after adding acidulated water to the mixture. The crude acid was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. It was obtained as colourless crystals from water, m.p. 145°, yield 24 g. It gives violet colouration with ferric chloride. (Found : C, 61.73 ; H, 5.23. $C_{10}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 61.85 ; H, 5.15 per cent).

γ-o-Hydroxyphenylbutyric Acid.—The above keto-acid (20 g.) was heated for 8 hours with amalgamated zinc (60 g.) and hydrochloric acid. The oily liquid was extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried, ether removed when the residue solidified on keeping in a vacuum desiccator, yield almost theoretical. It was crystallised from ether, m.p. 67°. (Found : C, 66.94 ; H, 6.70. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 66.66 ; H, 6.66 per cent).

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